

A Longitudinal Study to determine the Predictors of Job Satisfaction among Scientists and Engineers in a Research and Development Organization

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Abstract

Job satisfaction is a term used to describe how content an individual is with their job. It is a relatively recent term since in previous centuries the jobs available to a particular person were often predetermined by their parent's occupation. The research paper aims to focus upon the issue of Job Satisfaction with relevance to the scientific professionals working in one of the premier Research and Development organization which concentrates on indigenous technology development in the state of Tamil Nadu India. The purpose of the present research was to conduct a longitudinal, multivariate analysis of variables associated with the job satisfaction levels of the scientists and engineers working in different groups and Sections. The problem statement is based on whether it is only the compensation package which has the worth of retention and employee satisfaction or it is the overall organizational culture which has a pivotal role in retention and making employee satisfy. The results revealed that as against the common notion that the educated and learned scientists of our country are dissatisfied and are looking towards the careers in the western countries, the scientists are generally a satisfied lot and that beyond salary, it's the contingent rewards and recognition among co-workers that acts as the deciding factor for Job satisfaction among the intellectual and scientific population.

Key Words: Job Satisfaction, Research & Development, Multivariate Analysis, Organization Culture.

Introduction & Background

Job satisfaction is the degree to which people like their jobs. There are variety of factors that influence a person's level of job satisfaction; some of these factors include the level of pay and benefits, the perceived fairness of the promotion system within a organization, the quality of the working conditions, leadership and working relationships, and the job itself (the variety of tasks involved, the interest and challenge the job generates, and the clarity of the job description/requirements). Other influences on job satisfaction include the management style and culture, employee involvement, empowerment and autonomy enjoyed by the employee. Hence job satisfaction is a very important attribute which is frequently measured by many organisations.

Job satisfaction has been investigated in several disciplines such as psychology (Argyle, 1989), sociology (Hodson, 1985; Kalleberg and Loscocco, 1983), economics (Hamermesh, 1977, 2001; Freeman, 1978) and management sciences (Hunt and Saul, 1975; Spector, 1997) When we look at the kind of attention this issue has received in management research and try to understand the term Job Satisfaction as a management jargon, the term is loosely understood and viewed as a positive attitude towards one's work, which is global in nature and which results from many specific job related experiences (Sharma and Bhasker, 1991).

The increased demand for highly skilled professionals and the rapid changes being made in science, technology, and innovation imply that the skills shortage is unlikely to improve. Indeed, (Hay Group 2010) argued that there is a need for 200,000 new jobs every year in India, making the ability to attract and retain skilled professionals even more important over the next years. The shortage will be exacerbated as a result of the high prices, investment in several big projects, development of economic zones, and growing economic liberalization. It is becoming increasingly important, therefore, for general management and human resources professionals to understand the reasons behind the turnover. To the extent that specific aspects of jobs held by these skilled professionals contribute to high levels of turnover, and are within the control of the general management and human resources professionals, retention levels (e.g. job satisfaction and organizational commitment) could be increased through appropriate actions by management designed to minimize these problems. The effects of organizational characteristics variables (pay, promotion, supervision, co workers, and nature of work) on both job satisfaction and intentions to stay have been addressed by several studies in various countries as well as industries (Herzberg et al. 1959; Spector 1985; Igarria and Guimaraes 1993; Igarria et al. 1994; Tutuncu and Kozak 2007). One would hope that much of the findings will be applicable to R&D centres personnel. However, there is considerable evidence that R&D centres personnel differ from other employees on a number of values, attitudes, and motivational factors. It has been noted that R&D professionals have a value system which emphasizes independence, freedom, and autonomy to make decisions concerning their work (Clarke 2002). In addition, it has been reported that, R&D professionals have low levels of attachment to their employing organization (Chang et al. 2008). There is also evidence that R&D professionals generally respond more positively to intrinsic forms of reward and recognition such as praise and feedback from their peers (Clarke 2002). These findings have major implications for the management of R&D centers and further highlight the need to examine the impact of organizational characteristics on job satisfaction and intentions to stay among R&D centre employees. However, despite the great importance of the topic, a survey of the literature indicates that management research, for the most part, deals with the manufacturing and service sectors and lacks R&D focus. Researchers across disciplines have worked extensively exploring the issue of job satisfaction of their respective field and a significant body of literature has been created. JS has received in the production and service sector but there is a distinct lacuna in the study the JS levels amongst professionals employed in the scientific field. The premier Research Organizations in India are instated with the prime focus on the development of indigenous technologies in frontier areas and

strategic applications where technology is either denied or not available. Most of these technologies constitute the backbone of the country's economic and technological development and are a matter of pride. R&D is no longer an individual effort. It is essentially possible by holistic team contribution. Personnel including Scientist/Engineer from various disciplines in most of these organizations, spearhead the technological revolution in the country. Apart from the professional contribution they make, they are also the prime motive force in involving the younger generations in the national projects. It has been pointed out that a large number of scientists/engineers leave these organisations every year and nearly 50 per cent vacancies arise every year as a result of superannuation, resignation and VRS. Only 60- 70 per cent of the vacancies in the cadre of scientists/engineers arising every year can be filled up as, in spite of excellent HR practices and merit promotion schemes, these departments are not able to attract talent for high tech R&D work .Severe disparity existing between the IT industry and the government organisations both at the entry as well as the senior level." Study of factors that affect their job satisfaction and an analysis of the performance of such organisations are therefore important for R&D management theory and practice.

The Studies related to job satisfaction reveal that there was not a great deal of empirical agreements regarding the ingredients of Job Satisfaction. While some studies have been done for the industrial and service sector, relatively few studies have been done related to job satisfaction in the R & D Sector. This is significant because there are certain features which make the R & D institutions different from other organizations.

The focus of this study was upon studying the job satisfaction level of personnel in government run R&D organization. R&D being a multi – specialty operation involving inputs from various disciplines and is characterized by interplay of several domain areas and specialization. The success of such organizations depends primarily upon the synergy that exists between the various domains.

Research Methodology

Due to the limited research available on the job satisfaction level of the scientific community in the R & D Sector, the present research study has been taken up pertaining to a single Research & D organization which may lead to further studies to consider the scientists as the target population. The study was conducted in one of the premier R & D centre in Tamil Nadu, India. A Questionnaire was developed to measure dimensions of job satisfaction. The scientific personnel constituted the sample. The Human Resource & Development Head expressed great academic interest and whole heartedly supported the researcher in his endeavour. The respondents for the study were the scientists & engineers, because they were involved in R&D activities in varying capacities while performing different functions. The Questionnaire containing 32 Questions was used as the data collection tool. These Questions represented different factors of Job Satisfaction. Each question was on a five point likert scale. The researcher contacted a sample of 172 Scientists of the level of middle to high in the hierarchy of the centre. The sample was chosen using random Sampling by using the simple random number table with every second scientist selected from the attendance record. The questionnaires were distributed to the respondents and were given three to four days to give their responses. In all 170 scientists responded to the study (Response rate=99%). The questionnaire was tested for reliability and the Cronbach Alpha value was found to be .945. The Instrument was tested for validity through KMO and Bartlett's Test and the The KMO Value is 0.794 (>0.5). This shows that the survey instrument is Valid.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS

Table1 AGE

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
20-25	53	30.8	30.8	30.8
26-30	66	38.4	38.4	69.2
31-35	31	18.0	18.0	87.2
36-40	17	9.9	9.9	97.1
41 & above	5	2.9	2.9	100.0
Total	172	100.0	100.0	

Majority (87.2%) belonged to the age group 31-35 years

Table 2 Gender

Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	131	76.2	76.2	76.2
Female	41	23.8	23.8	100.0
Total	172	100.0	100.0	

76.2% of the employees are males
 23.8% of the employees are females

Table 3 Work Experience

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0-5	143	83.1	83.1	83.1
6-10	24	14.0	14.0	97.1
11-15	5	2.9	2.9	100.0
Total	172	100.0	100.0	

83.1% of the employees have 0-5 years of experience.

Table 4 CAREER DEVELOPMENT

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid High	162	94.2	94.2	94.2
Moderate	7	4.1	4.1	98.3
Low	3	1.7	1.7	100.0
Total	172	100.0	100.0	

94.2% of the employees are highly satisfied with their career development, 7% of the employees are moderately satisfied with their career development, 3% of the employees are less satisfied with their career development.

Table 5 WORK GROUP

Workgroup

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid High	112	65.1	65.1	65.1
Moderate	52	30.2	30.2	95.3
Low	8	4.7	4.7	100.0
Total	172	100.0	100.0	

65.1% of the employees are highly satisfied with their work group, 30.2% of the employees are moderately satisfied with their work group, 4.7% of the employees are less satisfied with their work group.

Table 6 Overall Job Satisfactions

Overall Job Satisfaction

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid High	55	32.0	32.0	32.0
Moderate	111	64.5	64.5	96.5
Low	6	3.5	3.5	100.0
Total	172	100.0	100.0	

64.5% of the employees are moderately satisfied with their job, 32% of the employees are highly satisfied with their job, 3.5% of the employees are less satisfied with their job

Table 7 Relationship with superiors

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid High	155	90.1	90.1	90.1
Moderate	17	9.9	9.9	100.0
Total	172	100.0	100.0	

90.1% of the employees are highly satisfied in their relationship with superiors, 9.9% of the employees are moderately satisfied in their relationship with superiors

Table 8 Rewards and Recognition

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid High	153	89.0	89.0	89.0
Moderate	19	11.0	11.0	100.0
Total	172	100.0	100.0	

89% of the employees are highly satisfied with rewards and recognition, 11% of the employees are moderately satisfied with rewards and recognition.

Table 9 Compensation

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid High	73	42.4	42.4	42.4
Moderate	70	40.7	40.7	83.1
Low	29	16.9	16.9	100.0
Total	172	100.0	100.0	

42.4% of the employees are highly satisfied with the compensation, 40.7% of the employees are moderately satisfied with the compensation, 16.9% of the employees are less satisfied with the compensation

Table 10 Role

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid High	167	97.1	97.1	97.1
Moderate	5	2.9	2.9	100.0
Total	172	100.0	100.0	

97.1% of the employees are highly satisfied with their job role, 2.9% of the employees are moderately satisfied with their job role.

Table 11 Working Environment

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	High	73	42.4	42.4
	Moderate	88	51.2	93.6
	Low	11	6.4	100.0
	Total	172	100.0	100.0

51.2% of the employees are moderately satisfied with the working environment, 42.4% of the employees are highly satisfied with the working environment, 6.4% of the employees are less satisfied with the working environment

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Multiple Regression analysis was used with Overall Job satisfaction as the criterion variable. The predictor variables are Organization, Career Development, Relationship with Superiors, Rewards and Recognition, Compensation, Job role, Workgroup, Working environment

Table 12 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
	.726 ^a	.526	.500	.37086

a. Predictors: (Constant), BENEFITS, CARRERDEVELOPMENT, REWARDSANDRECOGNITION, WORKINGENVIRONMENT, ORGANIZATION, COMPENSATION, ROLE, WORKGROUP, RELATIONSHIPWITHSUPERIORS.

b. Dependent Variable: Overall Job Satisfaction

The major predictors of Job Satisfaction identified are

Job Role

Compensation

Working Environment

Table 13 Coefficients (a)

Model	Un standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.112	.217	-.517	.606
	Organization	.002	.160	.001	.989
	Career Development	.038	.091	.024	.676
	Relationship with superiors	.141	.123	.081	.251
	Rewards and Recognition	.000	.116	.000	.998
	Compensation	.214	.048	.297	.000
	Role	.334	.215	.107	.122
	Workgroup	.201	.061	.221	.001
	Working environment	.211	.055	.241	.000
	Benefits	.250	.090	.169	.006

a. Dependent Variable: Overall Job Satisfaction

The Regression equation obtained (from Table 3.4.2) is:

$$\text{Job Satisfaction} = (0.112) + (0.02 * \text{Organization}) + (0.38 * \text{Career Development}) + (0.141 * \text{Relationship with superiors}) + (.000 * \text{Rewards and Recognition}) + (0.214 * \text{Compensation}) + (0.334 * \text{Role}) + (0.201 * \text{Workgroup}) + (0.211 * \text{Working environment})$$

ONE WAY ANOVA

Age and Overall Job Satisfaction

H0: There is no significant association between age and overall job satisfaction

H1: There is significant association between age and overall job satisfaction

Table 14 Age and Overall Job Satisfaction

ANOVA

Overall Job Satisfaction

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	3.844	4	.961	3.716	.006
Within Groups	43.196	167	.259		
Total	47.041	171			

INFERENCE

As the sig. value is 0.006(<0.05) null hypothesis is rejected. There is significant association between Age and Overall job satisfaction. (From Table 3.5.1)

Work Experience and Overall Job satisfaction

H0: There is no significant association between work experience and overall job satisfaction

H1: There is significant association between work experience and overall job satisfaction

Table 15 Work Experience and overall job satisfaction

ANOVA

Overall Job Satisfaction

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.380	2	.690	2.554	.081
Within Groups	45.660	169	.270		
Total	47.041	171			

INFERENCE:

As the sig. value is 0.81 (>0.05) null Hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant association between work experience and overall job satisfaction.

Compensation and Overall Job Satisfaction

H0: There is no significant association between Compensation and Overall Job Satisfaction

H1: There is significant association between Compensation and Overall Job Satisfaction

Table 16 Compensation and Overall Job Satisfaction

ANOVA

Overall Job Satisfaction	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	13.786	2	6.893	35.030	.000
Within Groups	33.255	169	.197		
Total	47.041	171			

INFERENCE:

As the sig. value is 0.000 (<0.05) null Hypothesis is rejected. There is significant association between Compensation and Overall Job Satisfaction.

Workgroup and Overall Job Satisfaction

H0: There is no significant association between Workgroup and Overall Job Satisfaction

H1: There is significant association between Workgroup and Overall Job Satisfaction

Table 17 Workgroup and Overall Job Satisfaction

ANOVA

Overall Job Satisfaction

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	14.348	2	7.174	37.084	.000
Within Groups	32.693	169	.193		
Total	47.041	171			

INFERENCE:

As the sig. value is 0.000 (<0.05) null Hypothesis is rejected. There is significant association between Workgroup and Overall Job Satisfaction.

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

Table 17 Compensation and Overall Job Satisfaction

Correlations

		OverallJobSatis	Compensation
Overall Job Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.528**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	172	172
Compensation	Pearson Correlation	.528**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	172	172

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

There is a strong positive correlation between compensation and overall job satisfaction

Table 18 Rewards and Recognition and Overall Job Satisfaction

Correlations

		Overall Job Satisfaction	Rewards and Recognition
Overall Job Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.298**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	172	172
Rewards and Recognition	Pearson Correlation	.298**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	172	172

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

There is a strong positive correlation between Rewards and recognition and Overall Job satisfaction.

Table 19 Role and Overall Job Satisfaction

Correlations

		Role	Overall Job Satisf
Role	Pearson Correlation	1	.359**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	172	172
Overall Job Satisf	Pearson Correlation	.359**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	172	172

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

There is a strong positive correlation between Role and Overall Job satisfaction.

Table 20 Career Development and Overall Job Satisfaction

Correlations

		Career Development	Overall Job Satisfaction
Career Development	Pearson Correlation	1	.093
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.226
	N	172	172
Overall Job Satisf	Pearson Correlation	.093	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.226	
	N	172	172

There is a positive correlation between Career Development and Overall Job satisfaction.

Conclusion

The Research was undertaken to identify the levels of job satisfaction among the employees in the R & D organization. A sample of 172 employees of the organization formed the part of the survey. The findings revealed that the majority of the employees were satisfied with their job. The project is also aimed at identifying major factors influencing job satisfaction. The project also suggested ways for improving the satisfaction level of the employees. It was heartening to note that in six out of nine factors the employees groups scored above the mean. It was also observed that many similarities existed between the groups. The study demonstrates that both groups of employees (Scientists & Engineers) are strongly satisfied with their nature of the work, co workers and supervision. An awareness of the activities or work of each department, section, and group could help employees to identify areas of his or her liking and since personnel from both the groups are similarly qualified, when a vacancy occurs, employee could apply for transfer to such area that is of liking, interest and personal strength. All employees at all levels, of varied educational

backgrounds, age, gender, position, and qualifications have an intrinsic need of appreciation and recognition of efforts. The centre should take appropriate steps to improve job satisfaction of all employees which would lead to increase in morale of its human resources, the most valued possession.

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